

**PHYSICAL INDICATORS OF 17-YEAR-OLD BOYS
INVOLVED IN SPORTS IN ANDIJAN REGION****Anvarjonova Nodirakhon****Andijan State University****Faculty of Natural Sciences, 2nd year master****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18031587>****ARTICLE INFO**

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KEYWORDS*sport, muscle, wrestling, mass, growth, pathological, diet, organism, shoulder, teenager.***ABSTRACT**

Today, many efforts are being made in our country to ensure that the growing youth are mentally and physically mature and well-developed, including the construction of a number of sports facilities and the fact that professional teachers in these centers are teaching young people in various fields. This article also discusses the physical indicators of adolescent children and statistically proves how beneficial sports are for the young organism.

Introduction

It is well known that the sports activity of students is characterized by certain specific qualitative indicators. Among them, the main physical qualities are muscle strength, speed, endurance, agility and flexibility. The development of physical qualities depends on the innate characteristics of a person. At the same time, the conditioned reflex mechanism is the leader in individual development. This mechanism provides the qualitative characteristics of the motor activity of students, their manifestation, specificity and mutual relationships. The study consists of studying the indicators of 17 boys from the Olympic and Paralympic Sports Training Center in Andijan.

The motor activity of people, including sports, is characterized by certain specific qualitative indicators. Among them, the main physical qualities are muscle strength, speed, endurance, agility and flexibility. Some authors also indicate the speed-strength indicator of a person as the main qualitative indicator. The development of physical qualities depends on the innate characteristics of a person. At the same time, the conditioned reflex mechanism is the leading one in individual development. This mechanism provides the qualitative characteristics of human motor activity, their manifestation, specificity and mutual relationships. The stimulation of the skeletal muscles of one side of the body (naturally, also the central nervous system) leads to the development of the same quality through the occurrence of similar reactions in the unstimulated parts of the nervous system and muscles of the other side of the body by a conditioned reflex.

In people who are not involved in sports, the reaction time of movement, that is, the movement of a finger in response to a light signal, decreases with age; in children aged 2–3, 500–800 ms are spent on this reaction, while in adults it is 190 ms. In athletes, this reaction takes an average of 120 ms in men and 140 ms in women. In highly qualified athletes involved in situational sports and sprinting, the reaction time of movement can be 110 ms or less, and in

stayers it can be 200–300 ms or more. They are less conscious of the manifestation of movement qualities than cyclic exercises, for which morphological, biochemical and vegetative changes in the body are more important. Most sports exercises require not only high-speed execution of movements, but also their execution in conditions of time constraints. Therefore, the development of physical agility is of great importance for success in such exercises.

The growth of a boy's body is not always the same throughout the year. For example, growth is much faster in spring and summer. It should be taken into account that each organism grows in height depending on its own individual characteristics. The rapid increase in body mass occurs in winter and autumn, and slows down in spring and summer. The assessment of mass gain also depends on the principle of height gain. A child's mass is considered pathological if it is more than 3 kg for his age. Growth and development occur on the basis of the processes of anabolism and catabolism in the body, and the process of anabolism is relatively strong in a growing organism. The period of adolescence is of particular importance in the physical and spiritual formation of a person, during this period the biological formation of a person ends and his maturity begins.

As a result of neglect of physical exercises, the physical development of children may lag behind. Obesity and cardiovascular diseases, which are common in children, can also be caused by lack of exercise. Lack of exercise is scientifically called "hyponkisia", in which muscles gradually atrophy due to a decrease in tone.

The main feature of a young organism is its continuous growth and development. Social and environmental factors influence this process. The main period of children's development falls on the school period. Therefore, the school routine, sports and physical education, and diet have a strong influence on the mental and physical development of students. It should be noted that the tissues and organs in the body work in a way that is interconnected through the central nervous system. Therefore, any adverse conditions and diseases not only disrupt the ability of individual organs and systems to function, but also change the functioning of the entire organism. During each disease, certain tissues and organs are more damaged. The characteristic feature of a healthy person is that he can quickly adapt to changes in external environmental conditions. At the same time, physical labor activity is good. However, the physical development, growth, mental and working abilities of all healthy children of the same age may differ from each other. It is known that learning activity consists of three interconnected parts: mental work, static tension and dynamic physical work.

According to the observations of hygienists, physiologists and clinicians, from the first day of school until the end of the senior year, students' lives are more static, and motor activity decreases. Such a ratio of static and dynamic work in the daily routine affects the health of students. During the period of adaptation of students of different school ages to the educational process, tension is observed in the neuropsychic state, the activity of active hormonal systems. Reflex changes also affect the respiratory and cardiovascular systems. As a result, the protective and adaptive properties of the organism decrease. These changes can occur throughout the school year and up to the senior year. This depends on the child's readiness for school conditions in terms of morphological and psychological indicators.

The working capacity of students decreases significantly by the second half of the year. In the process of adapting schoolchildren to educational loads, it is observed that, in addition to

the state of various functional systems, tension is also formed in the state of the hormonal system. Therefore, it is important to comprehensively study schoolchildren of different ages.

The observations were carried out mainly in the Olympic and Paralympic Sports Training Center in Andijan in two stages. In the first stage, the physical development indicators of young boys at the Olympic and Paralympic Sports Training Center were observed: height, body weight, chest circumference, and vital capacity of the lungs. The results obtained and their analysis were as follows. The physical development of the organism is body mass, shoulder width, and right and left hand strength. Body weight is one of the most sensitive parameters and has variable dynamics as a result of various diseases and nutritional disorders. Shoulder width shows the result of regular work movements. Right and left hand help determine the level of sports involvement.

The study of anthropometric indicators such as body weight (kg), shoulder width (cm), hand strength (kg/m) of 17-year-old children allows us to objectively assess the level of physical development of students participating in the study. In this case, body weight represents an individual response of the organism to the influence of external environmental factors and also depends on the constitutional characteristics of the organism, diet and norm of nutrition, metabolism, lifestyle and ecological climate conditions.

During the observations, 17 young male students of the Andijan city Olympic and Paralympic sports training center who regularly engaged in international sports were studied and analyzed, and their body mass was 65.30 - 2.11. 50-80 freestyle wrestling 65.20 - 2.10. 55-85 Sambo judo 60.50 - 1.64. 50 - 81. It is clear that the heaviest body mass was formed by children who engaged in international sports.

Shoulder width. International 44.90 - 0.53 41-49.5 Freestyle wrestling 44.96 - 0.42. 41.5-48.5 Sambo judo 42.50 - 0.70. 32-46. In this, children engaged in freestyle wrestling have a high indicator.

Right-handed children engaged in international sports 43.75-1.49. 30-50 Freestyle wrestling 44.50-1.44. 38-61 Sambo judo 41.20-1.64. 30-62. Freestyle wrestling gave higher results than other sports in the right hand.

Left-handed children engaged in international sports 45.00-1.63. 30-60 Freestyle wrestling 43.40 -1.25. 32-60 Sambo judo 42.60-1.81.30-60. Children engaged in international sports in the left hand had a high indicator.

Conclusion

Based on the above, we can say that the physical development of students is of great importance in the process of growth. In order to improve the physical development of students, it is recommended to include physical activity in the daily routine and perform various sports games and exercises in a complex manner, appropriate to their age. This, in turn, strengthens the muscles, cardiovascular system and immunity, and improves physical performance.

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